

LADYSTEEL: Assistance system to combat domestic violence on women

LADYSTEEL: Sistema de assistência ao combate à violência doméstica contra a mulher

LADYSTEEL: Sistema de asistencia para combatir la violencia doméstica contra la mujer

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Abstract:

Domestic violence is recognized as one of the most complex and worrying social phenomena, which, due to its large proportions, affects the lives of millions of women in the world. A significant part of women who experience this cycle of aggression omits the situations of which already have been or are still victims, not accomplishing any report against the aggressor. The current work, therefore, was elaborated from the mentioned social problem and a large number of omissions and difficulties that permeate it, resulting in a prototype of a system that could be used as a tool for government agencies, originating a more simplistic mechanism for accomplishing domestic violence reports, with its structure designed essentially for victims: a recondite device in an object present in their daily lives that, when pressed, will accomplish a report, sending a message to emergency contacts and sharing its location with competent authorities.

Resumo:

A violência doméstica é reconhecida como um dos fenômenos sociais mais complexos e preocupantes que afeta, por suas grandes proporções, a vida de milhões de mulheres no mundo. Seja por diferentes fatores, parte significativa das mulheres viventes nesse ciclo de agressões omite as situações das quais já foi ou ainda é vítima, não realizando nenhum tipo de denúncia contra seu agressor. O presente trabalho, portanto, foi elaborado a partir do citado problema social e do grande número de omissões e dificuldades que o permeiam, trazendo como resultado um protótipo de sistema que poderia ser disposto como instrumento de ofício à órgãos governamentais, originando um mecanismo mais simplista para a realização de denúncias de violência doméstica, com sua estrutura pensada essencialmente para vítimas: um dispositivo recôndito em um objeto presente em seu cotidiano que, ao ser pressionado, realizará sua denúncia, emitindo uma mensagem aos contatos emergenciais e compartilhando sua localização com as autoridades competentes.

Resumen:

La violencia doméstica es reconocida como uno de los fenómenos sociales más complejos y preocupantes, que por sus grandes proporciones afecta la vida de millones de mujeres en el mundo. Una parte importante de las mujeres que viven este ciclo de agresión omite las situaciones de las que ya han sido o siguen siendo víctimas, sin realizar ninguna denuncia contra su agresor. El presente trabajo, por lo tanto, se elaboró a partir de la problemática social mencionada y del gran número de omisiones y dificultades que la atraviesan, dando como resultado un prototipo de sistema que podría ser utilizado como herramienta por las agencias gubernamentales, originando un mecanismo más simplista para la realización de denuncias de violencia doméstica, con su estructura diseñada esencialmente para las víctimas: un dispositivo recôndito en un objeto presente en su vida cotidiana que, al ser presionado, realizará un reporte, enviando un mensaje a sus contactos de emergencia y compartiendo su ubicación con las autoridades competentes.

1. INTRODUCTION

Domestic violence against women, which, according to Aparecida Gonçalves (2018), to be faced, needs to be understood as a social phenomenon so that, at some point, there is justice and freedom for women with the possibility of a life without violence, continues, according to Nações Unidas Brasil (2021), corrosively widespread, affecting one in three women in the world throughout their lives. In Brazil, according to a survey entitled Violence and Murder of Women, by the Patrícia Galvão Institute (2013), data showed that 54% of the 1,501 respondents knew at least one woman who had been attacked by her partner. The existence of a continuous situation of aggression can result in impacts on victims for the remainder of their lives, even after the cycles of violence have been broken (Nações Unidas Brasil, 2021). According to this problem, this project is proposed, which aims to develop a prototype of a system that could be used as a service tool to combat domestic violence against women, being used by the Women's Service Center or government agencies, conceiving a new mean of intermediating contact between victims and service networks, based on the hypothesis that such a system, with a mean of sharing the victim's location with competent authorities and communicating with emergency contacts, coupled with a disguised reporting device to the point of going unnoticed, built using the resources of the Internet of Things, it can optimize the care of women and reduce the omission of aggressions, corroborating the reduction of harm to women and cases of femicide. In the subsequent chapters, all stages of development of the project will be presented, which was named LadySteel — Assistance System for Combating Domestic Violence Against Women.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Next, the theoretical foundations will be explained, which will be essential for understanding this article.

2.1. Definition of domestic violence

Domestic violence against women, which is defined in article 5 of Law 11,340/2006 of August 7, 2006, as “any action or omission based on gender that causes death, injury, physical, sexual or psychological suffering and moral or patrimonial”, continues, according to Patrícia Rosa (2021), to be one of the factors that placed Brazil in 5th place in the World Ranking of Femicide.

2.2. Index of incidents related to domestic violence

According to Ouvidoria Nacional dos Direitos Humanos (2022), in the first half of 2022 alone, Brazil registered more than 31 thousand denunciations and another 169 thousand violations involving domestic violence against women. This scenario of coercion causes biological, psychological, and social consequences for women, making it difficult for them to fully enjoy human and social equality (LUCENA et al., p.2, 2016). Considering these data, which assume greater proportions over time, the perspective of building solutions based on innovation and technology increases (SAES, 2012, p. 10). With this, technology, through an intermediary system and interconnected components, can make it possible to make denunciations and optimize assistance to victims using different and more comprehensive methods of existing models.

2.3. Victims of domestic violence do not report

According to Júlia Zeremba (2019), most victims of domestic violence do not report their partners to friends and family, or the authorities. In other words, it is a factor that greatly helps the aggressors' impunity and encourages other aggressors to commit the same crimes.

2.4. The use of technology in combat domestic violence

According to Bruno Santos et al. (2016, p.3), technology provides easier solutions to problems, replacing manual services and with greater consideration of time for more efficiency and speed. Based on such considerations and considering the contingency of idealized responses from innovation and technological factors (SAES, 2012, p.10), the objective is to answer the following question: how technology is capable of being used to combat domestic violence against women, saving the lives of countless victims?

2.4.1. Internet of things

Originating from the electronic miniaturization of equipment capable of communicating through networks, the Internet of Things, known as IoT, gave rise to a new reality (FILHO, 2016, p.8), providing everyday objects with computational capacity to connect to the Internet so that they can be controlled and accessed as service providers (SANTOS et al., 2016, p.2). According to Eduardo Magrani (2018, p.15), the Internet of Things is an alternative for the gradual growth of economic and social sectors, based on machine communication, presenting in this way, according to Sérgio de Oliveira (2017, p. .17), a new reality as something attainable and viable for monitoring various scenarios from automotive to sensory.

2.4.1.1. ESP32

Becoming an essential part of technological development in society, microcontrollers, with their high control capacity, cause a high demand for them (MORAIS, 2023, p.16). Among the microcontrollers, the ESP32 was developed, which is an open-source development board, with active WI-FI and Bluetooth, making it the ideal instrument for creating automation projects (ELETRÔNICA ÔMEGA, 2021, p. 5).

Figure 1 — ESP32 Model
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.1.2. Push button

Push Buttons are used to when pressed, activate a certain circuit. Its voltage is 3.3 Volts to 5 Volts, therefore a voltage higher or lower than that specified may cause poor functionality in the component (MCROBERTS, 2011, p.65). In this project, a push button will be used, with the function of sending a report to the authorities when the victim presses it in a risky situation.

Figure 2 — 12mm Push Button Model
Source: (USINAINFO, 2023)

2.4.1.3. GY-NEO6MV2

GY-NEO6MV2 is a GPS signal receiver module that operates at 3.3 Volts. It can communicate with the GNSS, that is, it can obtain information about its location in the world (GUIMARÃES, 2021).

Figure 3 — GY-NEO6MV2 GPS Module Model with Antenna
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.1.4. LED RGB

They are small LEDs that use RGB (Red, Green and Blue) technology, making it possible to adjust each of these colors to 255 possible levels, considerably increasing the light intensity that the LED can emit (MCROBERTS, 2011, p.49).

Figure 4 — LEDs RGB Model
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.1.5. Jumpers

Considerably thin wires which have the function of transporting energy between components (MONK, 2014, p.24).

Figure 5 — Female-Female Jumpers Model
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.1.6. Protoboard

Board with several points that is used to assemble circuits. The biggest advantage of breadboards is that they do not require soldering, making them a practical and perfect component for prototypes (MCROBERTS, 2011, p.46).

Figure 6 — Breadboard models with 170 and 400 points
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.1.7. Switched power supply

It is a source that converts the voltage received from another energy source when it opens and closes an oscillator made up of semiconductors, which will dissipate the power through these oscillations, meaning that the source does not need to heat up (QUADROS, 2021).

Figure 7 — Switched power supply model with 9 volts
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.1.8. Resistors

They are small electrical devices used to limit the passage of current, normally between electrical components (MCROBERTS, 2011, p.47), very useful for regulating the passage of energy between components and preventing them from overloading.

Figure 8 — Model 10 Ohm Resistors
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.1.9. PHP

According to Converse and Park (2003, p.3), PHP stands for PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor and is a high-performance, object-oriented server-side language, aimed at open-source scripts, which can be integrated into HTML. The PHP code runs on the server, generating HTML that is then sent to the browser. The browser receives the results of executing this script but does not know what the source code was (PHP, 2023). Data made available by W3Techs (2023) shows that, in 2023, 77.4% of all websites on the internet will use PHP in their composition. The language at the time of publication of this document is version 8.2, showing that PHP continues to be widely used.

```

1  <?php
2  //Programa em PHP que exibe as tabuadas
3  //Definindo a tabuada em que irá iniciar:
4  $tabuada_inicial = 1;
5  //Definindo a tabuada em que irá terminar:
6  $tabuada_final = 2;
7  //Estrutura de repetição para a seguinte situação:
8  //Enquanto não houver chegado até a tabuada final...
9  while($tabuada_inicial <= $tabuada_fim){
10     //...o programa irá apresentar as tabuadas, com os números de 1 a 10:
11     for($i = 0; $i <= 10 ; $i++){
12         echo $tabuada_inicial . ' x ' . $i . ' = ' . $i * $tabuada_inicial;
13         echo '<br>';
14     }
15     //Quebra de linha após o fim da tabuada:
16     echo '<br>';
17     //Incremento para que a próxima tabuada se inicie:
18     $tabuada_inicial++;
19 }
20 ?>

```

Figure 9 — PHP code example
Source: From the author, 2023.

In the figure above, the PHP code displays the multiplication tables from one to the specified number, in this case, the number two, multiplying the counter by all numbers from one to ten, with spacing between each multiplication table. Next, a figure with the result of the code above will be displayed.

```
1 x 0 = 0
1 x 1 = 1
1 x 2 = 2
1 x 3 = 3
1 x 4 = 4
1 x 5 = 5
1 x 6 = 6
1 x 7 = 7
1 x 8 = 8
1 x 9 = 9
1 x 10 = 10

2 x 0 = 0
2 x 1 = 2
2 x 2 = 4
2 x 3 = 6
2 x 4 = 8
2 x 5 = 10
2 x 6 = 12
2 x 7 = 14
2 x 8 = 16
2 x 9 = 18
2 x 10 = 20
```

Figure 10 — PHP coding result
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.4.2. Laravel

Laravel is a framework for web applications in PHP that uses the MVC (Model View Controller) pattern, which in addition to providing a complete structure, facilitates the integration of the application with the database and unit and integration tests (LARAVEL).

2.4.3. C++

C++ is a low-level object-oriented programming language derived from the C language, capable of generating fast and efficient programs. Generally used in developing applications that require performance (DAVIS, 2016, p.2). A C++ program requires compilation after coding, which means compiling the source code of one or more files and transforming them into a machine language file, which the computer can read and execute (MICROSOFT LEARN, 2023).

```

1 //Definindo em quais pinos digitais os LEDs estão ligados
2 #define LED_RED 2
3 #define LED_GREEN 4
4 #define LED_YELLOW 5
5
6 void setup() {
7 //Iniciando os LEDs como saída
8 pinMode(LED_RED, OUTPUT);
9 pinMode(LED_GREEN, OUTPUT);
10 pinMode(LED_YELLOW, OUTPUT);
11 }
12
13 void loop() {
14 //desliga LED amarelo e liga LED vermelho
15 digitalWrite(LED_YELLOW, LOW);
16 digitalWrite(LED_RED, HIGH);
17
18 //aguarda 500 milisegundos
19 delay(500);
20
21 //desliga LED vermelho e liga LED verde
22 digitalWrite(LED_RED, LOW);
23 digitalWrite(LED_GREEN, HIGH);
24
25 //aguarda 500 milisegundos
26 delay(500);
27
28 //desliga LED verde e liga LED amarelo
29 digitalWrite(LED_GREEN, LOW);
30 digitalWrite(LED_YELLOW, HIGH);
31
32 //aguarda 500 milisegundos
33 delay(500);
34 }

```

Figure 11 — Example C++ code for ESP32
Source: From the author, 2023.

In the figure above, you can see a C++ code that turns the three LEDs connected in a loop on and off, with a 500-millisecond wait between each LED activation.

Figura 12 — Result of coding in C++
Source: From the author, 2023.

2.5. Modelo de entidade e relacionamento (MER)

This project involves a system composed of an electronic circuit and a website based on the Laravel framework. The electronic circuit was designed with the primary purpose of allowing victims in risky

situations to discreetly activate a hidden button that sends a denunciation to the authorities responsible for cases of domestic violence. Below is the circuit of the device.

Figure 13 — LadySteel System Circuit
Source: From the author, 2023.

Due to its activation in emergencies, the device is designed to be disguised and minimize detection by the aggressor. Next, a photo of the disguise created to hide the system circuit will be shown.

Figure 14 — LadySteel System Disguise
Source: From the author, 2023.

When accessing the website, the user will come across a confectionery page called Soufly, which contains information and curiosities about the confectionery, along with a famous phrase from the cook Palmirinha. Its main function is to disguise the site so that potential attackers do not know what the site is really about if they happen to have access to it. This makes it difficult for the attacker to be aware of the victim's use of the platform.

Figure 15 — High Fidelity Wireframe: Disguisedd home page
Source: From the author, 2023.

The true home page of the LadySteel system is revealed when one of the two buttons on the confectionery page is clicked. One of them is a slice of cake above Palmirinha's phrase and the other is a butterfly present in the footer, next to the page's copyright. The image below shows both buttons, indicated by a red arrow.

Figure 16 — High Fidelity Wireframe: Desguised home page's bottom
Source: From the author, 2023.

The next wireframe constructed is the home page, where information on domestic violence against women is presented, these being references to the law itself and indicative data on the aforementioned social problem. The menu consists of three links: the Home itself, Contact Us, a contact form page and, About, where information about the LadySteel project is displayed.

Figure 17 — High Fidelity Wireframe: Victim's profile page
Source: From the author, 2023.

The website will have three main functions: registering victims in the system, managing denunciations made by devices, and managing the agents responsible for reporting. Starting with the victim's role, she will configure the device directly through the website, where she will provide her personal information and the requested device data that she already has in her possession. After that, she will be able to manage her respective data. Next, a prototype of the victim's profile graphical interface will be shown.

Figure 18 — High Fidelity Wireframe: Victim's profile page
Source: From the author, 2023.

Denunciations will be managed by staff from the bodies responsible for handling these incidents. Functions will be available on the platform for viewing and accepting denunciations. Simultaneously with the acceptance of the reports, a message will be sent to two contacts previously registered by the victim when creating the account in the system. This measure aims to provide greater comfort to women, especially when making denunciations. The next figure will show the prototype of the attendant's pending denunciations page.

Figure 19 — High Fidelity Wireframe: Pending denunciations page
Source: From the author, 2023.

The figure below shows the graphical interface made for the attendant with the details of a report made:

Figure 20 — High Fidelity Wireframe: Details of the denunciation
Source: From the author, 2023.

The supervisor will be responsible for managing the attendants and devices, therefore, they will have the following functions: viewing active devices, registering, editing, and listing attendants, as well as inactivating their accounts. Furthermore, the supervisor will be able to access daily, weekly and, annual reports related to denunciations. The following figure shows the interface of the annual report page on accepted denunciations.

Figure 21 — High Fidelity Wireframe: Supervisor's annual report page
Source: From the author, 2023.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research method used will be based on ways of obtaining quantitative data, which, according to Gil (2017), results are presented in numerical terms. The data will be organized in a way that proves the aforementioned hypothesis. The project will be developed based on:

- Electronic references: Use of electronic articles and research already completed in the last 5 years that present the social impacts of domestic violence against women with the presence of informative data;
- Bibliographic research: The concepts analyzed will be: “Public policies to combat domestic violence”, “Brazilian laws on domestic violence” and “Mechanisms for reporting domestic violence”. Research is based mainly on material made available by the Federal Government or institutions linked to it.

The use of documents and bibliographies will aim to demonstrate, through authors and recent research, that many cases are omitted by victims because they cannot be alerted or reported at the time of the act. They will have a critical bias to expose how many deaths are due to the inefficiency of reporting channels. Finally, it will be possible to conclude that a new immediate violence warning system could minimize extreme situations such as femicide and the harm caused to women.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Despite all the basis in the construction of the work, the hypothesis that a technological system to aid in the fight against domestic violence, equipped with sharing the victim's location with competent authorities and messaging emergency contacts, with a disguised device, can optimize care of women and reduce the omission of aggressions, corroborating the reduction of harm to women and cases of femicide, cannot be confirmed or refuted to date, as an indefinite period of usability and safety tests would be necessary to verify whether the product it could present any type of risk to the victims who would use it and it would fulfill its function without any room for error. Therefore, although the response to the hypothesis is not entirely favorable, there are no arguments, until the moment this document is written, that refute it, leaving open for both factors: future confirmation or refutation.

5. CONCLUSION

Given all the reasons presented, we can say that technology can be used to combat domestic violence against women in countless ways, one of which is what was constituted in this project: the development of a way to optimize and reinvent the reporting system that is provided by government bodies, but which still has many gaps. For future improvements, we hope to develop even more ways to make reports, creating increasingly portable devices that can be anywhere, without possible problems with significant travel or connection.

Finally, despite the small flaws that still exist in the present work because it is only a systematic prototype that would deal with a phenomenon that still occurs massively in our society, we, as a group, consider the results to be satisfactory, and we hope that, soon, can be considered a fundamental step in inspiring other researchers and developers to explore the potential of technology to promote meaningful change.

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